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Connectome-based diffusion using graph neural networks for generating high fidelity synthetic fMRI data

Scientific Students' Association Report

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Kivonat

Az elmúlt időszakban a mélytanulás számos orvosi alkalmazásban jelentős előrelépést tett, többek között a gyógyszertervezés és az orvosi képelemzés területén. Ezeknek a modelleknek kiemelkedően sok adatra van szükségük, hogy igazán jó és megbízható eredményeket hozhassanak. Azonban az orvosi képképző módszerekkel szerzett adatok (például CT vagy MRI) relatív ritkák és nehezen hozzáférhetők. Például egy MRI felvétel nem minden páciensnél elvégezhető egészségügyi okokból és a felvételek készítése sok időt és anyagi forrást kíván.

Ezen okokból az orvosi adatok nehezebben beszerezhetők, ami indokolja az adat augmentációs eljárások alkalmazását, mint például a szintetikus adat generálás. Dolgozatunkban diffúziós modelleket alkalmazunk az adat generálásra, amelyek korábbi eredmények alapján alkalmasak valóság-hű képek generálására. Ezen modellek orvosi adatokra való alkalmazásában azonban nagy akadály az adatok nagy mérete, különösen 3D és 4D-s képképzési technikák esetén, mint az MRI.

A gráf neurális háló (GNN) feltörekvő modell típus, amit egyéb orvosi alkalmazásokban előszeretettel alkalmaznak; lehetővé teszi a mélytanulási módszerek gráfokon való alkalmazását. Ennek komplex belső struktúrával rendelkező adatok esetén van nagy előnye: gyakran reprezentálnak gráfokkal természetben előforduló kapcsolatokat, mint a szociális hálókat, molekulákat; vagy ebben az esetben az agyi konnektomokat.

A dolgozatunkban kihasználjuk, hogy az fMRI felvételek konnektomok és ROIk által tömörebben leírhatóak és az adat ezen reprezentációján tanítunk egy diffúziós modellel GNN-ek használatával. Ezáltal le tudjuk csökkenteni a modell erőforrás igényét, miközben a diffúziós modellek előnyeit megőrizzük. Végül az ebből származó kimeneteket egy variációs autoenkóderben kiegészítő információként felhasználva fMRI képeket generálunk.

Abstract

In recent years deep learning has contributed to numerous medical fields in significant ways, such as drug discovery and medical image analysis. These models need an outstanding amount of data to yield good, reliable results. However, medical imaging data like MRI and CT scans are relatively scarce, compared to natural data such as text and images. These scans pose some challenges, for example MRI imaging is not possible in some patients due to medical reasons and the scans are both time-consuming and expensive.

For these reasons, medical data is more difficult to attain, which creates the need for data augmentation techniques that can counteract this deficiency, one of which is data synthesis. In this paper we use diffusion models to generate synthetic data, which have proven to be capable of generating high-fidelity images. However, applying them to medical data is very demanding, due to the large size of each sample of input data, especially in case of 3D and 4D data, like MRI scans.

Another emerging method, often used in other areas of medical research is Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), which offer the possibility of using deep learning methods with graphs. The use of these methods often presents an advantage when working with data that has a complex inner structure: graphs are commonly used to represent relationships in naturally occurring structures, like social networks or molecules; and in our case brain connectomes.

In this paper, we exploit the dense representations of brain fMRI scans that connectomes and ROIs offer, by creating a diffusion model that works with this form of data by utilizing GNNs. This reduces the resource intensiveness of our model, while retaining the high-fidelity, diverse samples provided by the diffusion process. Finally, the resulting data is used as supplementary information in a Variational Autoencoder as a means of generating voxel images.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Since the rise of deep learning in the early 2010s, it has been applied in many different research areas with outstanding results. The medical field is no exception[45][32], as deep learning models have been used from novel drug discovery[2], to protein folding[37], to early disease detection[52]. These advances have unlocked new opportunities and can provide guidance to patients and physicians alike.

Deep learning methods are generally known for being data-hungry, meaning they need a large number of samples to produce the outstanding results they are capable of[1]. Usually this is not a problem with natural data such as text and RGB images, however medical imaging data, such MRI and CT scans, poses a problem, as it is much harder to access. This is partly due to the cost associated with the machines and taking scans and the cost of creating high-quality datasets, as they usually require many hours of work by experts in their respective fields. Furthermore, accessing these datasets is difficult due to privacy concerns and the sensitive nature of said data.

The scarcity of data in the field warrants the use of augmentation techniques to improve the performance of the models, with the limited number of samples available. Common traditional image augmentation techniques, such as affine transformations, are often not as successful in this domain due to the unique properties of medical images[14]. This suggests data augmentation should be more tailored in this case than for common RGB images, but there are many methods that are applicable, one of these techniques is synthetic data generation to artificially increase the number training samples.

The first major breakthrough in deep learning was Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which enabled quick and accurate image processing tasks on medical imaging data, such as segmentation, and classification. In 2015, [43] released the UNet architecture for neural image segmentation, whose success has led to it being the basis of many projects applying deep learning methods to medical data. As the field progressed, new methods emerged, notably Generative Adversarial Networks[17] (GANs). These models have two competing neural networks: one is the generator, which creates synthetic images like those in the training dataset, while the other, the discriminator, has the task of deciding which image comes from the real dataset and which is fake. After training is complete, this approach allows for the generation of synthetic samples via the generator network, however this has its own disadvantages. While after the generator is trained, it can produce high-fidelity samples, the training process is made difficult by having to find a balance between the two networks.

Later, Variational Autoencoders[25] (VAEs) emerged as an alternative class of models for data generation. These models have an encoder part that downsamples the input data

until a bottleneck is reached, wherefrom the decoder tries to reconstruct the original input from the reduced data available in the bottleneck. For sampling, the decoder can be used to reconstruct images from the bottleneck, which the model has not seen before. While having a stable training cycle, as opposed to GANs, VAEs struggle to create as high quality and diverse samples as GANs [10].

A new class of models emerged in 2020, when [20] introduced the Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPMs) or diffusion models for short. Training diffusion models consists of two parts: the forward noising process and the backward process. During the forward process, noise is added to the training samples, according to a noise scheduler, until the image’s structure is destroyed. The backward process consists of iteratively removing noise from the sample, resulting in a clear image. This is an ill-proposed problem, and therefore, a neural network is used to predict the noise in the given input at a certain timestep during the noising process. Sampling is done by taking random noise and passing it through the network until we get a clear image. Since their introduction, diffusion models have been the state of the art in synthetic image generation because of their ability to generate high-quality, diverse samples. However, due to the long process of denoising, which is on the order of hundreds or thousands of steps, DDPMs are incredibly resource intensive[42].

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are a relatively new class of models that have been developed to be able to work on the many kinds of naturally occurring graph data: things with complex structures, or cases where connections between items are important. These benefit especially from being modeled by graphs[24]. In the field of biomedical research, we can find a lot of these datasets, from molecule prediction[54] and drug interaction[57], to advances in genetic research[51]. Having a method that can take the intricacies of such complex, interconnected systems into account when making predictions can be invaluable in medical research[56].

There have been a variety of methods to work on graphs before, mostly from a classical mathematical algorithmic perspective, such as random walk-based models[38]. With the advent of Graph Convolutional Networks[28] (GCNs), there is a computationally simple way of using the well-established method of convolutional layers on graph data, allowing for processing of large amounts of data and the creation of architectures that fit into backpropagation-based deep learning solutions. This model and most modern graph architectures utilize the *message passing* principle: information is aggregated in the graph along edges as nodes pass messages to each other.

The brain can be segmented into different parts based on its anatomical structure. These regions of interest (ROIs), coupled with functional connectomes, which describe the relationships between the activations of certain brain regions, can be extracted from fMRI scans with a somewhat resource-intensive process using brain atlases prepared by medical experts for specific tasks. They provide a dense representation of the structure and functional relationships between the parts of the brain. Our proposed method tries to alleviate the resource intensiveness of the diffusion process by applying it to the denser representations of ROIs and connectomes, as opposed to the 3D or 4D fMRI scans themselves. Crucially, ROIs and connectomes are in the form of graphs, enabling us to use efficient GNNs significantly reducing the size of the model used in the diffusion process. These graphs are then used to condition a VAE to generate high-fidelity voxel-based fMRI images.

Chapter 2

Background

This chapter will give in-depth explanations on the various topics included in our work. The first two sections give the theoretical background behind MRI and fMRI, the imaging techniques the data comes from, then give an introduction to the dataset and the forms of data we worked with. We continue by giving an introduction to deep learning and generative modelling, with a focus on the theoretical background of the methods we used. The last section explains GNNs and the Graph U-Net architecture that we build on.

2.1 MRI and fMRI Imaging

Non-invasive medical imaging techniques, such as MRI, X-ray, and CT scans, are essential tools in medicine, allowing physicians to understand the internal structures and functions of the body without the need for surgery. These techniques are invaluable for their ability to produce high-resolution images of soft tissues, making it ideal for assessing the state and function of internal organs. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), stands out, as it produces its high-fidelity images, while using no ionizing radiation, making possible its repeated use in patients[36].

2.1.1 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

At its core MRI technology builds on a physical phenomenon called Nuclear Magnetic Resonance. This phenomenon builds on the property of certain atomic nuclei, that when exposed to a strong magnetic field, align themselves to it. One of these is the Hydrogen atom, which is abundant in all parts of the human body. When the aligned nuclei are perturbed by a specific frequency of RF signal, they go out of alignment with the original magnetic field, absorb the energy of the signal, and start to precess, due to their inherent angular momentum. During this precessing, the nuclei emit the absorbed energy, which is unique to each different type of tissue in the body, due to the difference in their density and other factors[39].

MRI machines build on this phenomenon by providing a strong, constant magnetic field \vec{B} , then sending short pulses of localized RF signals, with the help of the gradient coils, which causes the previously mentioned misalignment. As the atoms realign themselves with \vec{B} the MRI machine measures the signals they emit, and construct an image made of three-dimensional pixels, called voxels.

2.1.2 Signal Detection

Signal detection in MRI machines is described by the following equation:

$$S(t) = N \sin(\theta)\omega \cos(\omega t), \quad (2.1)$$

where $S(t)$ is the result signal as a function of time, N is number number of atoms in the examined tissue, θ is the flip angle of the tipped nucleus, the angle between the magnetic field \vec{B} and the magnetized vector of the nucleus. ω is the angular momentum of the nucleus given by the Larmor equation as $\omega = \gamma\vec{B}$, where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, a constant inherent to the nucleus. Taking a closer look at this equation we can see what influences the strength of the captured signal. Since N and γ can not be influenced by us, we are left to manipulate \vec{B} . Increasing the strength of \vec{B} has a directly proportional effect on the strength of our signal. Indeed, this circular magnet is crucial to the workings of MRI machines.

After capturing the signals, the constructed image's appearance will be influence by several key parameters of the scan. Two of the most important parameters, set by the MRI technician before the scan begins, is the Time Echo (TE) and Time of Repetition (TR). The key to produce a good image is the time when we sample the signal emitted by the nuclei. Since different tissue have different characteristics their signals will decay differently. TE is the time between the delivery of the RF pulse and the sampling of the echoing signal. TR is simply the time between the successive pulse sequences. It influences the amount time the nuclei have to realign themselves with \vec{B} before becoming misaligned again. Setting up these parameters differently, leads to unique images. Most common are T₁-weighted images that are taken with short TE and TR times (around 14 and 500 milliseconds respectively), and T₂-weighted images which are captured using longer TE and TR times (90 and 4000 milliseconds respectively)[8].

2.1.3 Functional MRI Imaging

Functional MRI of fMRI extends the capabilities of MRI by measuring brain activity, via a method called Blood Oxygen Level Dependant Constant[16]. This technique exploits the haemodynamic response, in which when a part of the brain is activated, blood flows the region (after an initial dip). This surge of oxygenated blood increases the ratio of higher-than-normal oxygenated hemoglobin. Oxygenated hemoglobin has different magnetic properties than deoxygenated hemoglobin, which causes measurable changes in the magnetic field in the activated region. This difference is measured by fMRI, allowing detection of neural activity. The ability to capture neural activity in a non-invasive way is invaluable in both clinical and research settings.

2.2 Brain fMRI Processing

Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) can be used to provide detailed images of human brain that reflect localized changes in blood flow and oxygenation induced by sensory, motor, or cognitive tasks[9]. An MR image or volume is made up of individual cuboid elements called voxels, the number and size of which reflects the quality of the scan. An fMRI data set from a single session can either be thought of as t volumes, one

taken every few seconds, or as v voxels, each with an associated time series of t time points[47]. High-resolution images can be captured, which permit the detailed analysis of brain responses, and as the method is non-invasive and low-risk for patients, data can be collected in a wide range of studies. fMRI reflects neural activity: the presented task increases local neuronal activity, which in turn increases metabolic rate, which also means increased blood flow, which translates into an increased MRI signal. This process also means that the changes in the fMRI are delayed compared to the stimuli by 1-2 seconds[9].

Before any meaningful analysis can be conducted, the raw four-dimensional data needs to be thoroughly pre-processed[49]. Slice-timing correction makes sure that when viewing a volume all of the voxels have been acquired at the same time, and motion correction is applied to make sure each volume is aligned with every other one. Smoothing methods are applied to reduce noise and artifacts.

2.2.1 ROIs and Brain Connectomes

To better understand and analyze activation maps resulting from this statistical process researchers often turn to brain atlases, which are sophisticated templates created as the average of many brains, that give a common coordinate system and also contain important information about the brain at every voxel. Using these brain atlases it is possible to segment images into what are called regions of interests (ROIs). The average activation of each of these regions is determined and used to draw conclusions about how this brain region participates in a given task, especially if we are able to extract information about how these regions interact with each other[41].

Interregional correlations between fluctuations of activation can reveal a lot about these interactions. These correlations change during the performance of a task, which shows that the regions interact differently in different situations. Various methods are available for assessing connectivity, to yield a sort of brain graph describing how connected these regions are, often referred to as connectomes. A typical brain connectome is comprised of nodes for each brain ROI and edge weights that denote the connectivity strength between two ROIs.[5]

2.2.2 The HCP Dataset

The HCP dataset was collected by WU-Minn HCP consortium in connection with the Human Connectome Project. The goal of this project is to facilitate research into mapping out the human brain. For this reason the project collected high-quality neuroimaging data in over 1100 healthy young adults for the free use of researchers[50]. The dataset encompasses both resting state and task-based MRIs and was collected by 10 institutions in different parts of the world.

Our work focuses on the task-based portion of the dataset, where subjects were instructed to imagine moving various parts of their body while the fMRI took place, creating 5 classes in the data based on the body part - tongue, left and right hand, left and right foot respectively. The data can be downloaded from their ConnectomeDB¹ in an already preprocessed state as well: creating an easy to use dataset, where the end user wouldn't need to have all the necessary medical knowledge and computation power to do the initial, required preprocessing steps was also a focus of the project. For this purpose common

¹<https://db.humanconnectome.org/app/template/Login.vm>

automated preprocessing pipelines were created to accomplish low-level tasks, such as surface generation, artefact removal and alignment to standard space[15].

2.3 Deep Learning

Artificial intelligence, is field that has its origins set in the mid 20th century. Its largest branch is machine learning in which instead of a set of predetermined rules, models learn characteristics of training data, and make predictions for new data, based on the patterns they have learned. Deep learning has emerged as a groundbreaking technique within machine learning in the last decade and has since grown to be the most influential branch of the field, affecting every part of our lives, as well as financial markets and countless industries.

2.3.1 Neural Networks

Neural networks are computational models inspired by the human brain's structure, consisting of interconnected layers of neurons, that process data in ways that mimic on a high-level, how biological neurons transmit information. Each neuron in a layer is connected to neurons in the subsequent layer, and these connections are associated with learnable weights that adjust as the network trains, allowing it to capture intricate relationships in data. Because of the stacking of layers into 'deep' neural networks and the usage of non-linear activation functions, neural networks are universal approximators, meaning they can learn to approximate any function with any precision.

In training, neural networks utilize backpropagation and gradient descent to optimize their weights and biases. Using the chain rule and derivation backpropagation computes the gradient of the loss function with respect to each weight by propagating the error backward from the output layer to the input layer, effectively learning how to correct the model's errors. Gradient descent, then adjusts the weights to minimize the error iteratively. The equation for updating the weights of the network is the following:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{i,j}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} \frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} \frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{i,j}}, \quad (2.2)$$

where E is the error of the forward pass through the network, $w_{i,j}$ is weight j in layer i , which we are updating, o_j is the output of the neuron after the activation function, net_j is the output of the neuron after multiplying the input by the associated weight. These calculations can be independently calculated for each neuron in a layer and multiple samples. This leads to neural networks performing billions of matrix multiplications.

Some of the factors that enabled neural networks to rise is popularity come not from the models, but the software and hardware architecture that enables quick and easy training of them. Specifically Graphical Processing Units on the hardware side, which are exceptional at parallel computational tasks due to the architecture. On the software side, automatic differentiation and other deep learning libraries make architecting and experimenting with neural networks simple.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are neural networks designed for spatial and image data, using convolutional layers to apply learnable filters over the input. This process generates feature maps that capture spatial relationships, allowing CNNs to detect pat-

terns like edges and textures effectively, while greatly reducing the number of parameters needed as compared to regular feed-forward neural networks. Stacking convolutional layers enables CNNs to learn increasingly complex feature hierarchies, from simple shapes to intricate patterns, making them the basic building block for all image recognition tasks.

2.4 Generative Modeling

Generative Modeling refers to a process, in which after models finish training, they can generate samples that were not part of their training dataset, based on the distribution learned during training. Generative Models started out in the mid-2010s with GANs, and exploded in popularity and abilities since the release of ChatGPT for text generation, and DALL-E or Stable Diffusion for image generation.

2.4.1 Variational Autoencoders

Variational Autoencoders, introduced by Kingma and Welling in 2013[25], are a type of generative model that combine deep neural networks with probabilistic modeling to generate high-quality images. VAEs are designed to learn probabilistic representations of data, where the latent space follows a specified distribution - usually Gaussian, which allows for controlled sampling and generation of new data. Instead of learning a deterministic encoding, as in standard autoencoders[3], VAEs use a probabilistic approach, learning a distribution in the latent space that approximates the training data distribution. The model is made up of two parts, the encoder and the decoder. The encoder usually uses a series of convolutional and pooling layers to downsample the input data into the size of the bottleneck, and the decoder uses convolutional and unpooling layers to reconstruct the input from the bottleneck.

The goal of VAEs is to minimize the negative Evidence Lower Bound. This loss function is made of two primary components: reconstruction loss and KL-divergence. Reconstruction loss is usually simple (e.g.: pixel-wise Mean Square Error), and it measures how well the reconstructed image $p(x|z)$ resembles the input data x . Reconstruction loss can be written as follows:

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(z|x)}[\log p(x|z)],$$

where x is the input sample, z is the latent variable, $p(x|z)$ is the reconstructed image, and $q(z|x)$ is the approximate posterior (i.e.: the output of the encoder). The second part of the loss is the KL-divergence, which measures the difference between two probability distributions.

$$D_{KL}(q(z|x)||p(z)),$$

where $q(z|x)$ is the approximate posterior and $p(z)$ is the prior. Essentially this loss forces the distribution of the approximate posterior to be close to the distribution of the latent variable z . Combining these two losses we get the loss of the VAE:

$$L_{VAE} = -\mathbb{E}_{q(z|x)}[\log p(x|z)] + D_{KL}(q(z|x)||p(z))$$

Once trained, the model can generate new data by sampling from the prior distribution $p(z) = \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ and passing the sampled z through the decoder, producing synthetic data samples that resemble what would be the original input data.

2.5 Diffusion Models

Denosing Diffusion Probabilistic Models, take a completely different approach to generative modeling than GANs and VAEs. Popularized in 2020 by Ho et. al[20] diffusion models take inspiration from thermodynamics, particularly Langevin dynamics[53]. Instead of generating a sample in one step, images undergo an iterative process of noising and denoising. Diffusion models have since become the state of the art in a wide variety of image synthesis tasks, such as unconditional and conditional image synthesis, image inpainting, text-to-image, and text-to-video generation.

2.5.1 Forward and Backward Process

During training DDPMs, images undergo a forward-, and backward noising process. During the forward noising process, noise is sampled from an Isotropic Gaussian distribution according to a noise scheduler, then added to the input image. This process is repeated usually, from several hundreds, several thousands of times, until the input image x_0 gradually shifts to pure noise version x_T . This process can be written as such:

$$q(\mathbf{x}_t|\mathbf{x}_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_t; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t}\mathbf{x}_{t-1}, \beta_t\mathbf{I}),$$

where x_t and x_{t-1} are the noisy images at timestep t and $t-1$ and β_t determines the amount of added noise at timestep t and is sampled from the noise scheduler. The aforementioned noise scheduler is crucial part of the diffusion process, as an incorrect noise scheduler can prevent the model from learning entirely. Although this depends on the exact problem, as it can be seen in Figure 2.1, a linear noise scheduler adds too much noise too quickly, therefore turning the image into pure noise sooner than desired, to the effect that later step don't contribute anything meaningful.

On the other hand a cosine scheduler adds less noise in the earlier stages of the forward process, and more at the end when the finer details have already been destroyed. In practice, going through the entire noising process for each timestep and each sample is impractical due to the training loop of DDPMs (which will be explained later). Therefore we need to be able to sample noise at any timestep t , with only x_0 and the noise scheduler available. This can be done using the reparametrization trick[26] and some other transformations[48]:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \sqrt{\alpha_t}\mathbf{x}_0 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t}\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \text{ where } \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}), \quad (2.3)$$

where $\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$. Equation 2.3 will be used at training to create a noisy sample at timestep t in one calculation, instead of having to go through each step until t .

The backwards process, what is in essence sampling, is the task of iteratively removing noise from the corrupted input image, which starts out as randomly sampled noise. The distribution this describes is $q(x_{t-1}|x_t)$, but because this distribution is intractable, we approximate it with a neural network:

Figure 2.1: An image depicting linear (top) and cosine (bottom) noise schedules at certain timesteps from 0 to T . [35]

Figure 2.2: An image depicting the steps of the forward and backwards diffusion process. [20]

$$p_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_{0:T}) = p(\mathbf{x}_T) \sum_{t=1}^T p_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t), \quad (2.4)$$

$$(2.5)$$

$$\text{where } p_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}; \mu_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t), \Sigma_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)) \quad (2.6)$$

Our network predicts $p_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t)$, specifically $\mu_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ and $\Sigma_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$. In practice however, our network usually predicts the pixel-wise noise directly. This can be written in the following way:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(x_t - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \tilde{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t) \right) + \sigma_t z,$$

where $\tilde{\alpha}_t = \sum_{i=0}^t \alpha_i$, $\epsilon_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ is the mean predicted by our network, and σ_t is the variance. Empirically DDPMs were found to produce better results with a fixed variance, although some papers use variance that is also learned[20].

These equations allow us introduce the training and sampling loops for DDPMs, as can be seen in Figure X [Would probably be nicer to create this table wit latex]. The training loop consist of sampling a timestep t from a uniform distribution, and sampling noise from a uniform distribution. Then the neural network predicts the noise based on the input image x_0 , the timestep t and α_t , which can be calculated from β_t sampled from our noise scheduler. Finally the loss is calculated as a simple MSE and backpropagated through the network. Sampling is done by going through the backwards process from timestep T , iteratively denoising our input according to Equation 2.5.1, until timestep 0 the result of which is a clear image. These algorithms also demonstrate simply, why DDPMs are so computationally demanding.

2.5.2 Improvements in the Diffusion Process (DDIM, Class Conditioning)

Although DDPMs introduced in the previous section give the basis for the diffusion process, there have been further improvements on the baseline architecture. We will introduce two of these, which were significant in our work. Firstly, Denoising Diffusion Implicit Models[48] (DDIMs) improve on the sampling time of DDPMs, by decoupling the number of steps needed for training from the number of steps needed for sampling. The reduction of sampling steps can greatly accelerate the process of synthesizing new samples, while keeping the same high-quality and diverse properties of DDPMs. DDIMs also enable deterministic sampling, which can be very important. They achieve this by relaxing the Markovian assumption in the backwards process, and skipping some steps. More precisely, while DDPMs execute the backwards process as a sequence of conditional probabilities, DDIMs compute the denoised image at a certain timestep directly. The modified sampling equation is:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \sqrt{\alpha_{t-1}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{x}_t - \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t} \epsilon_\theta^{(t)}(\mathbf{x}_t)}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \right) + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_{t-1} - \sigma_t^2} \cdot \epsilon_\theta^{(t)}(\mathbf{x}_t) + \sigma_t \epsilon_t$$

, where $\epsilon_\theta^{(t)}$ is the noise predicted by our network, and setting σ_t to 0 leads to deterministic sampling. DDIM sampling while training a DDPM is especially useful, as samples can be generated quickly at validation epochs, during the lengthy training process.

Class conditioning further enhances diffusion models by enabling generation conditioned on specific categories, allowing for the tailored production of samples for particular classes. It can be implemented in several ways, with the most common being passing an embedding of the class labels to the noise predicting network. This approach guides the diffusion process and allows it to learn different characteristics of the passed labels. As a result it becomes possible to generate sample belonging to a certain class, which can be especially useful in medical imaging tasks, where it may be important to differentiate between conditions found in the image.

2.6 Graph Neural Networks

The power of graphs as a data representation method is in their versatility. The level of abstraction they provide makes them suitable for use in many fields, as connections between items or molecules or people are vital in understanding complex natural systems. Given their usefulness, it is a natural progression to want to extend machine learning methods to this realm as well: reasoning and prediction based on graph-based data has become a more and more commonly researched topic in recent years[55].

Since graph data is very complex in structure compared to other data commonly used in ML, such as images, it requires specialized methods. Graph Convolutional Networks[27] (GCNs) expand on the idea of CNNs, which are commonly used in image processing. Observing from a graph perspective, an image can be considered a very special case of a graph, where pixels are nodes and their neighbours can be determined from the grid. This type of network generalizes the concept of local convolutions from the image domain to general graphs.

$$H^{(l+1)} = f(H^{(l)}, A) = g\left(\hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}\hat{A}\hat{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}H^{(l)}W^{(l)}\right) \quad (2.7)$$

In each layer new *node features* are calculated based on the values in the previous layer (similarly to pixel values in a CNN). Each node’s values are calculated based on its neighbours’ values and a learnable weight matrix. Equation 2.7 shows how a single layer of the network operates: A is the adjacency matrix of the graph ($\hat{A} = A + I$), \hat{D} is the diagonal node degree matrix for the purpose of normalisation, and W is the learnable weight matrix, g is a non-linear activation function, most commonly ReLU in practice.

Figure 2.3: Visualization of a GCN accumulating information. [44]

These local graph convolutions are a good analogue of image convolutions and also serve as an approximation of spectral convolutions in graphs, which are way more resource intensive[28]. Furthermore, as illustrated by Figure 2.3 as the network gets deeper, information can travel further and further through the network, aggregating more and more information from the structure into the individual nodes.

2.6.1 Edge and Node Prediction

Common tasks of a GCN include graph, edge and node prediction. Graph prediction assigns a label to an entire graph, while node and edge prediction focus on individual elements of the graph; the latter two are going to be relevant in our use-case. The base output of a graph network is one vector per node which is usually referred to as a *node embedding*. The use of this for node prediction is very straightforward, this can be trained to represent a class or some other value for a node. For graph or edge prediction however, there is more needed.

Edge prediction commonly refers to the task of finding the most probable but not present edges in a graph, which is useful in a variety of applications, for example recommendation systems. In our case however, it is not the presence of links we want to predict, but their strength. There are multiple commonly used techniques for edge prediction using the node embeddings generated by a graph network[29], that are just as suitable for providing continuous results as they are for binary ones. In case of GCNs these methods rely on information about pairs of nodes.

2.6.2 Graph U-Net

Since U-nets have been such a successful model type in convolutional networks, there has been an effort to find an analogue in graph convolutional networks as well. Graph U-nets[13] follow the original principles of the U-net architecture: the encoder-decoder structure, the skip connections and the general architecture, as seen on Figure 2.4. The convolutional layers are replaced by GCN layers and for standard pooling and unpooling layers which do not have an obvious graph equivalent, since they rely on locality in images that is not present in general graphs, novel layers have been developed for graph pooling and unpooling.

Figure 2.4: Visualization of the graph U-nets architecture. [13]

2.6.2.1 Graph Pooling and Unpooling Layers

Graph pooling layers enable downsampling on graphs by adaptively selecting nodes to build a smaller graph from existing nodes, while preserving edges. The selection method is similar to a traditional k-max pooling: the highest k values are preserved after the operation. The top k nodes are selected based on a learned 1D projection, to a vector \mathbf{p} :

$$y_i = x_i \mathbf{p} / \|\mathbf{p}\|,$$

the nodes are kept which retain most of their information when projected to \mathbf{p} . After the selection has been made, the adjacency matrix is updated to only include these nodes and the corresponding rows are extracted from the feature matrix via a gate operation, using matrix multiplication and a sigmoid operation, which makes \mathbf{p} trainable by backpropagation.

The unpooling layer, unlike image upsampling layers, can only work in connection with a graph pooling layer for which it performs an opposite action: the adjacency matrix is restored to its state prior to the the pooling layer and the node feature matrix is distributed into a shape corresponding to this larger number of nodes, having zero values for newly reappearing nodes.

Chapter 3

Related work

This chapter details how other works in the field of medical image synthesis, diffusion models and graph neural network relate to our work. Some of them directly inspired our model architecture, while others are important works in their fields.

3.1 Medical Image Synthesis

Image synthesis in medical imaging has leveraged advancements in generative models, particularly for scarce data like MRI and fMRI. Generative models like GANs, VAEs, and diffusion models have enabled generating synthetic samples in the likeness of real images in the limited amount of training data available.

Early work in medical image synthesis, such as [6] explored and demonstrated how GANs could generate MRI and CT images to expand training datasets and achieve better results in some tasks. They used a PCGAN network to augment small MRI datasets, generating realistic images that improved model performance on segmentation tasks measured by the DSC metric. Their approach highlighted the improvements in performance of the models trained on the datasets augmented with synthetic data. They found that in the case of the MRI dataset, the less samples were in the original dataset, the more pronounced the effect of augmentation was, until a point where synthetic data could not make up for the lack of real data.

Diffusion models, popularized by Ho et al.[20], have recently become a key focus in generative modelling, offering high-quality results and greater control over image fidelity. Rombach et al. advanced this area with Latent Diffusion Models[42], which operate within a compressed latent space to significantly reduce computational costs while retaining image detail. By applying diffusion in this reduced space, they were able to maintain the high-fidelity of generated samples while using less compute resources. Although not in the medical domain, the idea of delegating the computationally demanding diffusion process to be done on a compressed representation inspired our work.

The paper [34] by Gustav-Müller et al. introduces a conditional latent DDPM model Medfusion. The authors evaluate the performance of the model on several medical datasets and compare it to different GAN architectures. They highlight the challenges of generating high-quality synthetic data with GANs, due to architectural like mode collapse and their unstable training behavior. Results show that Medfusion, outperforms GAN models in diversity, realism and key quantitative metrics like FID and MS-SSIM.

Work by Fan et al. [30] delves into the use of diffusion models for graph generation. It provides an overview of several different types of diffusion models, and details use cases for molecule and protein folding. The paper highlights the effectiveness of diffusion models in generating realistic samples, and finds the method of generating graphs with DDPMs promising.

It is also worth mentioning the work of Dorjsembe et al.[11]. Although the paper is brief, this method of directly generating three-dimensional fMRI voxel images is the process we are trying to improve upon.

3.2 Graph Generation

Graph generation is a less popular and less widely adopted technique than image generation, but that is not to say that it is without precedent. The problem has a rich history from a mathematical standpoint: mathematical models for random graph generation have been present for a long time, such as the Erdős-Rényi graphs[12] and Barabási-Albert graphs[4]. In more recent times and with more machine learning relevance, deep graph generative models are especially interesting in the bio-informatics: molecule and protein generation are both studied topics[33]. With regards to images, scene-graphs are often used in general-purpose image generation and can also be generated themselves[7].

There are different approaches to graph generation, one-shot generation being similar to how image generation work: the entire graph is created on the output of the model, either as an adjacency matrix or as an edge-list. GAN networks and VAEs specialized to generate graphs are in this category, as well as diffusion models. Sequential generation is more similar to the way that text generation works: a stream of nodes or edges[18].

There have also been instances of graph generation with a diffusion framework[33], with varying methods, mainly for the purpose of molecule generation, which is very useful in drug discovery.

3.3 Super-Resolution of Brain Connectomes

For the more specific case of generating brain connectomes, we can turn research into creating high-resolution versions of low-resolution brain connectomes[40]. This super-resolution is a crucial aspect of neuroimaging research, as higher resolution imaging techniques and data processing pipelines can be rather costly and more susceptible to noise; meaning a way to achieve consistent super-resolution would make data acquisition much easier. In this paper the authors set out to find a reliable method for this task using a diffusion model Dif-GSR.

This network is very different from our solution however, as the authors opted to treat the connectome as a grayscale image and use a U-net for images, with CNN layers in their model. They assign this choice to better scalability of CNNs compared to GCNs, but as our connectomes are only of size 42×42 , we are not looking for scalability in this regard, but rather the ability of GCNs to better capture the very complex structure of the brain connectome.

In an earlier paper[23] the same authors were looking at this same problem and created a graph super-resolution network using a modified graph U-net (Section 2.6.2). The model, GSR-Net, consists of a graph U-Autoencoder block and a graph super resolution block,

where the former is a graph U-net altered in a way that it is capable of working with the specifics of a connectome. Since these graphs do not feature binary edges but are complete graphs with edge weights, the adjacency matrix is treated differently, message passing is weighted by these edge values.

While the goal of this model is quite different from our own, the graph U-net used here was a very important inspiration for our modified version: since this also works on connectomes, the changes made had to be quite similar. The adjacency matrix needs to remain made of continuous floats, preventing the use of certain boolean shortcuts and the final goal of the network is not node prediction. But since in the GSR-Net the output of the graph U-Autoencoder is used as input for the super resolution block, which was not necessary in our case, the final processing of the node features needed to be quite different and we needed to find our own solution.

Chapter 4

Methods and Implementation

4.1 Main Idea

The goal of our project is to generate synthetic three dimensional fMRI brain scans. Since doing this in the original fMRI domain is incredibly resource intensive as data is always at least 3 dimensional, with the available computational power only very small resolution samples could be generated. Our idea was to take the generative part of the model to different space, by generating a more compact representation of the brain scan. We settled on the activation values of the ROIs and the generated connectomes for this purpose.

The ROI+connectome representation first has to be extracted from each sample of the dataset and then we use these as the input for our diffusion model. Since the connectome at this point is not an image but rather a sort of brain graph, we opted to create a model different from most DDPMs, by creating a specialized graph U-net, that can serve as the neural network inside the diffusion model that predicts the noise. To do this we adapt the original graph U-net to work in this setting, by adding time and class conditioning and edge prediction techniques.

The resulting generated connectomes and ROI values are then used to condition the bottleneck of a VAE, which has been trained to generate MRI scans with the original images of the same dataset, using the original ROI and connectome values. The goal is to make sure the VAE learns how to generate scans that correspond to the information fed at the bottleneck; this way we are able to generate ROI and connectome samples, which can be turned into high-fidelity MRI samples with significantly less resource usage than if we were generating the MRIs in the first place.

4.2 Data Preprocessing

Our architecture requires three separated types of data, the fMRI scan and ROIs and connectomes corresponding to the scan. Of these the HCP dataset only contains the fMRI scan, and the rest needs to be computed in a preprocessing pipeline. The ROI values can be extracted with the help of an atlas, which describes the regions of the brain we need corresponding ROI values. We only focused on sensory motor tasks, therefore we filtered for brain regions activated during these tasks (in practice this means 21 ROIs for each side of the brain, so 42 altogether). With the filtered atlas, a mask can be constructed, to block out unwanted parts of the brain during the extraction. Understanding the format and meaning of the data used in the preprocessing (e.g.: What ROIs and connectomes

are and how to calculate them) is difficult as it requires knowledge in the medical domain. Thanks to a team of doctors who communicated with our supervisors, as well as the very well documented nilearn python package, we had help in understanding the data we worked with.

After extraction is complete we get a timeseries of ROI values for each patient. This means a tensor of size $284 \times 16 \times 42$, (time \times repeatedmeasurements \times ROIs). To validate the correctness of the preprocessing we trained a Support Vector Machine to classify the ROIs based on the performed task. For this the ROIs need to be standardized per subject, and separated by task. For this we had a Python script from previous works that generates a csv file with the times slices and the task performed at that time interval. This file is essential in separating the relevant parts of the scans from the noise where no task is performed. The scans contain measurements for 5 tasks performed twice, so in total 10 for each patient, with 16 repeated measurements taken by the MRI machine (Before going into any model the mean value of these 16 steps was taken). This means 124 of the 284 long scan is noise.

Once the preprocessing was correct the SVM achieved 90-95% accuracy. For calculating the connectomes we used the nilearn package’s ConnectivityEstimator class. The subject-wise calculated ROIs were separated by tasks as well, and connectomes were calculated for each task separately, because the measurements across different tasks is significantly different, therefore calculating the connectomes with the tasks mixed, would not yield meaningful results. Lastly, for the input of the GNN, ROIs were standardized dataset-wise. For training the VAE, fMRIs samples were standardized according to precalculated values for each slice in the previously mentioned csv file.

4.3 Proposed Architecture

The model consists of a diffusion block and an autoencoder. The diffusion block is trained on the ROI values and connectomes to also generate ROI values and connectomes, which are used to condition the autoencoder at the bottleneck.

Figure 4.1: Visualization of the model architecture, focusing on the flow of data

One of the main advantages of this architecture is that the two parts of the model can be trained separately. The autoencoder is trained to be able to reproduce scans while being supplied the corresponding connectome. At sampling time are the two models are both used. The diffusion model generates a connectome and only the decoder part of the autoencoder is used to generate novel samples.

4.3.1 Diffusion Block

We started out by using our own implementation of DDPM and DDIM models, and later transitioned to the denoising-diffusion-pytorch package. This package is commonly used for experimenting and training diffusion models, and is much less likely to have implementation error than our own models. The package provides an easy interface to train diffusion models with our own custom networks though we had to add some unused parameters to our model, that were unnecessary requirements of the package. Another advantage of this package is it enabled easy DDIM sampling, which we used with 200 steps, instead of the 1000 used for training the DDPM. We found that this package lacks the capability for training a network with class conditioning, so we extended the package for our experiments involving class conditioning.

4.3.2 Graph U-net

The graph U-net used in our model is a modified version of the architecture proposed in [13]. The connectome is used as the adjacency matrix in the U-net, the connectivity values between ROIs are the weights of edges in the graph. Since we have singular ROI values available for each of the nodes these were distributed along an identity matrix to create a better input for the network and since the U-net requires symmetry and we will be looking to generate both connectomes and ROI values, the full input is the concatenation of the ROI filled identity matrix and the connectome. In this case, since the connectomes are 42×42 , the input of this part of the network is batch size $\times 42 \times 84$.

The model has the same number of blocks in both directions, comprised of one GCN layer and one graph pooling layer in the down direction and one graph unpooling layer and one GCN layer in the up direction, with a connecting bottom GCN layer. Corresponding blocks of the same size are connected via skip connections. Conditioning (with the main concern being time conditioning) is applied at every block by calculating scale and shift vectors via a small MLP.

The output of the last block is thus the same size as the input of the first one and it gets separated into node features that are used for ROI values calculation and node features that are used for connectome calculation. The ones used for ROIs are sent through a final GCN layer where they are reduced to single value per node and then distributed along an identity matrix to preserve the symmetry of the data. For the connectome however, as each value represents an edge between two regions, the other half of the output gets pairwise concatenated and passed through an MLP to determine one value per edge for the connectome.

Figure 4.2: Visualization of the graph U-net architecture, focusing on the flow of data

4.3.3 Variational AutoEncoder

The VAE was not considered the main part of our work by us. To this effect we choose to use an implementation provided by the latent-diffusion Github repo¹. This model granted us the option to train a VAE that learns representations on 3D data. The class had to be modified in minor ways to fit in with the rest of our codebase, and we made two major changes to it. Firstly we recalibrated the loss function to enable the model to train on our dataset. Secondly, we extended the model with the capability to condition the bottleneck with the ROIs and connectomes. This was done by a small CNNs with a fully connected layer at the end that takes the $2 \times 42 \times 42$ size ROI and connectome and creates an embedding with the same size as the bottleneck. Then the bottleneck is conditioned on the embedding by performing Adaptive Instance Normalization[22] on them.

4.4 Experiments

This section will detail the different experiments we conducted on our models. We focused mainly on the GNN as it is the central part of our architecture. The VAE remained largely the same, with only minor changes to accommodate the conditioned training and sampling.

4.4.1 GNN Experiments

Since there are not many examples of similar architectures built with GNN networks, we had to do some experiments to try and figure out which setups would lead to better generation results in the end. Because of the wide variety of options to try and the lack of guidance on which ones could be successful in which combination, we opted to try out new ideas in a fail fast method: we inspected the results of the model after a set number

¹<https://github.com/CompVis/latent-diffusion>

of epochs and if the connectome visually worsened or did not improve, we opted to use a different method in the future.

4.4.1.1 Edge Prediction Method

Since the base output of the model is just node features and there are various methods to convert them into edge predictions[29] we had to try a few to see what would work well with our model. In the implementation of the graph U-net we included a switch that can take None, 'scalar' and 'mlp' values and makes experimenting with this easier. The None value keeps the original vector of the output, without any transformations applied. In this setting the network tries to learn the noise/denoised values as if they were features of the nodes. This is the easiest method to implement but this way it is not taken into consideration how each edge represents the connection between two edges.

To better accomplish this, the 'scalar' method takes each resulting node embedding and computes the scalar product of each node pair to build the new matrix. In case of the 'mlp' option the node embedding get pairwise concatenated to represent their respective edges, and then are passed through a small MLP to calculate an edge strength for the pair of nodes. Here the concatenation makes sure that both nodes are considered in the calculation.

In the final version we ended up using the MLP to calculate the connectome as it yielded better results than the base method and with the scalar product approach we discovered that it led to generated samples looking almost identical.

4.4.1.2 Class Conditioning

As mentioned before in Section 2.5.2, introducing a class conditioning in a DDPMs can give a significant boost to their performance. Since our dataset had labels in the form of the body part corresponding to each sample that the subject was instructed to imagine raising, we could try this method in our model as well. We implemented a very simple version of this by extending the diffusion package we used with the class conditioning being passed to the U-net and in the GNN concatenated the one-hot vector representing the class to the time conditioning to execute both kinds at once.

Sadly this implementation did not result in improved performance, the resulting generated samples tended to have prominent bands of a single value instead of resembling the input connectomes. We have not yet found the reason for this development and we believe it still might be a good idea to further experiment with conditioning, perhaps trying to create a more refined implementation.

4.4.1.3 Loss Calculation

Since the connectome is supposed to be a symmetric matrix, we tried changing the graph U-net's loss function to reflect this in some form. We implemented a version of loss calculation where only the lower triangle matrix of both the result and target were considered during calculation: keeping the generation of the upper half as a sanity check, but concentrating on the lower half. This did not noticeably impact the resulting generated samples, so we opted for removing it, choosing to keep the model simpler if possible.

Chapter 5

Results

In this chapter, we will show and evaluate the results of our work. We used a mix of quantitative and qualitative metrics, which is common in image synthesis tasks. As we will explain, not all of our planned evaluation methods could be executed.

5.1 Metrics

Evaluating image synthesis tasks requires multiple different approaches. For one, quantitative metrics like Fréchet Inception Distance[19] (FID), Peak Signal to Noise Ratio[21] (PSNR), and Structural Similarity Index Measure[21] (SSIM) are key to obtaining an objective view of the quality of the generated samples. On the other hand, especially in image synthesis tasks, qualitative evaluation is important to assess the visual quality of the samples, as numerical measurements don't always align with visual representations. FID uses an InceptionV3 network to calculate the distance between the extracted features of real and generated samples, PSNR measures the ratio of the signal (i.e., the important parts of the image) and noise in the reconstructed image, and SSIM, unlike PSNR, measures not the pixel values, but structural aspects of the samples.

5.2 Results

As a baseline, we can compare these metrics to those measured on a pixel-based 3D DDPM architecture[46]:

Method	FID	PSNR	SSIM
Ours	400.8233	13.4702	0.0535
Pixel-based	20.4152	27.5278	0.8442

Table 5.1: Comparison of results on quantitative metrics between our method and a pixel-based DDPM method.

As the numerical metrics show, our model fails to produce any meaningful results with the VAE conditioned by the generated ROIs and connectomes. However, these metrics are not an accurate representation of our results. For that we need to look at some generated samples.

Figure 5.1: Samples from the VAE, on the left a sample generated by the decoder conditioned by our generated ROIs, on the right a sample generated during a validation epoch.

In Figure 5.1, on the left is a generated sample that is conditioned by our synthetic ROIs. It is noisy, with no resemblance to a sample from the training dataset. On the right is a sample that was generated in a validation epoch and conditioned with real ROIs as a way of monitoring the quality of the generated samples during training. This looks very similar to training samples, although it still contains some artifacts, like small chunks outside of the brain. This comparison points to our generated ROIs having the opposite of the desired effect, as they completely destroy the image. To further understand why this happens we need to take a look at some ROI samples.

On the left is a sample from our training dataset, and on the right is a sample generated by our network. It is important to mention that this sample is not representative of the samples generated by our network, as they mostly devolve into meaningless high and low values with no structure at all. The left side of each image shows the ROI values multiplied by an identity matrix (this is because we pass the ROI and connectome as a concatenated input to the GNN), and on the right side is the connectome, which functions as the adjacency matrix for the ROIs. The training sample shows how certain parts of the brain have a greater correlation in activation with others, while some have a negative correlation. Similarly, some ROIs show higher values during activation while others remain inactive.

In contrast with this, our samples show little resemblance to varying and correlating values on the connectome and instead collapse into mostly one value. While this sample shows varying ROI values that somewhat resemble the training sample, there is still some noise left in the space where the matrix should be empty, and on most of the images, the ROI values along the diagonal (or even the entire matrix) collapse into the same value. For the quantitative evaluation of ROIs, we planned to use the same method as validating the correctness of our preprocessing - training an SVM to classify the ROI based on the task. However, since we could not get any meaningful results from class-conditioned training, this was not possible. For unconditioned samples, some sort of unsupervised learning method (e.g., K-Means clustering) could be used, though the quality of these samples didn't necessitate it.

Taking a look at the loss shown in Figure 5.3, we can see a part of the problem. Although it might look like it from the loss decreasing orders of magnitude within a couple of epochs, training does not in fact converge. Instead the loss fluctuates between 10^{-2} and 10^2 , which

Figure 5.2: On the bottom is one of the better samples generated by our GNN, and on the top a sample from the training dataset. ROIs are on the left and connectomes are on the right.

is an outstanding difference, and is most likely why our model does not converge. It is the magnitude of the change, and not simply the stagnation, as it is common for diffusion models to still learn meaningful features while the overall loss does not decrease.

Nevertheless, our results can not be interpreted as a failure of this architecture. As Figure 5.2 shows, our network is capable of generating some good samples, which gives us reason to believe that this architecture will be capable of learning meaningful representations from the data. Furthermore, this architecture achieved significant results in terms of resource intensiveness. We were able to reduce the total number of parameters by about 80%, from the 33.6 million parameters in the pixel-based diffusion model using a 3D-UNet architecture to a total of around 6 million parameters in our models, 500 thousand for the GNN and 5.5 million for the VAE. Our approach not only reduces the number of parameters and the resources needed for training but decoupling the diffusion process from the large pixel-based VAE enables rapid experimentation, which was not possible previously with pixel-based DDPMs. With the VAE trained once, different GNN models can be rapidly trained and tested with the VAE because an epoch of the GNN training takes around 5 seconds on the entire dataset on an RTX 3090 GPU, compared to 20 minutes for the VAE (and pixel-based diffusion approach).

Figure 5.3: On the the top a is the loss, per epoch during training our GNN, and on the bottom the loss per epoch during the same training run.

Chapter 6

Future work

Overall, our project has been successful in verifying that our proposed method is indeed capable of generating fMRI samples while using only a fraction of compute and time that a standard diffusion model working image-to-image would. While the quality of our results is not meaningful at this time, we are looking forward to trying out multiple ways to improve the model and hopefully reach a state where we can generate high-quality samples with great efficiency.

6.1 Architectural Refinement

There are a number of places where our base architecture could be modified and tested to see if it helps with the quality of the generated samples. One of these is a more refined implementation of class conditioning. The graph network could also be altered: the number of blocks, the activation functions used, the formatting of the data as it flows through the network, and the way ROI values and connectomes are extracted at the end of the U-net.

6.2 Hyper-parameter Optimization

There is a very large number of possible hyper-parameters across the entire model that have an incredible amount of possible combinations that might or might not impact the final results in significant ways. The noise scheduling, the learning rate, and other optimizer settings, as well as dropout, are all things that have been observed to considerably alter model performance. We have tried to alter these values, but so far we have not conducted a methodical hyper-parameter sweep. Connecting the model to a tool that can automate such a process is a future goal of our work.

6.3 Experiments on Other Datasets

Data and data quality are crucial questions in any deep learning application and even more so in medical data. In our case, the data that we used was verified to be of good quality, and the pre-processing was also monitored. But while we believe that the data is good, it could be interesting to see how the model works on other data sources and fMRIs of different origins.

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